

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Clubroot of crucifers: Control Strategies Based on Spore Concentration in Fields

Plasmodiophora brassicae is an economically significant soil-borne pathogen causing clubroot disease in *Brassica* species resulting in considerable yield losses among crucifer crops. The pathogen is difficult to manage since its resting spores are viable in soil for many years and the cultural practices of the disease are limited.

To provide a broader assessment of the health status of Estonian agricultural soils, we determined the concentration of *Plasmodiophora brassicae* from soil samples collected from Estonian commercial fields. Analysis of the results of large-

scale monitoring in Estonia found that estimating the spore concentration of *P. brassicae* from soil can help farmers in crop rotation planning. Cultivation of cruciferous crops can be recommended in fields with low levels of inoculum (green dots). In case of moderate infection (yellow dots), it is advisable to apply all preventive measures, including liming and growing clubroot-resistant varieties. In the areas marked in red, cruciferous vegetables should be excluded from the crop rotation, Attention should be paid to the sanitation of field equipment to prevent transmission of the pathogen to other fields.

1. Infection burden of *P. brassicae* in collected samples by region, divided into risk classes according to the number of spores in the soil sample.

2. *P. brassicae*.

KEYWORDS

Plasmodiophora brassicae, *Brassica*, crucifer crops

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